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Supporting Analysts in Exploratory Process Analysis: A Multi-Perspective Approach to Sequential Filtering

Master's Thesis

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Abstract

Exploratory process mining allows analysts to investigate event logs through iterative filtering and visualization. However, as multiple filters are applied in sequence, it becomes increasingly difficult to trace how each step influences the resulting datasets. Current process analysis tools typically display only the final filtered result, providing limited insight into the intermediate transformations. This lack of transparency can hinder analysts' understanding of how filtering decisions shape the data and, ultimately, the conclusions drawn from it.

This thesis addresses that challenge by introducing a visualization-based framework that supports analysts in systematically tracking and visualizing the effects of sequential filtering. The proposed framework retraces each filtering operation, reconstructs the lineage of subsets, and visualizes their relationships using interactive charts. This allows analysts to maintain an overview of their analysis path, compare included and excluded data, and reflect on how sequentially applied filters influence process metrics such as case duration, number of events per case, and average time between events.

The framework was implemented as a prototype and demonstrated on three benchmark event logs (BPIC 2017 [1], Road Traffic Fines [2], and Sepsis [3]). A user study with process analysts was conducted to evaluate the extent to which the framework supports analysts in exploring event logs, how users perceive its implementation aspects, and in which contexts or stages of their analytical workflow they consider the framework most valuable. The results indicate that the framework is intuitive, easy to use, and supports understanding of how filtering steps affect the result. Participants valued the ability to explore analyses from multiple perspectives, validate assumptions, and communicate insights more effectively. Identified improvement areas include enhanced interactivity, scalability for long filter sequences, and support for domain-specific metrics.

Overall, the thesis contributes a conceptual and practical approach for making sequential filtering in process exploration more transparent and interpretable to process analysts. By combining the visualization of filtering steps with the comparison of resulting subsets, it aims to enable more reflective, flexible, and systematic analytical practices in exploratory process mining.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter outlines the motivation and context for this thesis in Section 1.1. It introduces the problem statement and main research question in Section 1.2, and illustrates the approach and contributions in 1.3. Finally, Section 1.4 provides an overview of the report.

1.1 Motivation and Context

Process analytics is a subfield of process mining [5], which itself is a branch of data analytics that applies analytical methods to event logs generated during the execution of real-world processes [6]. When process analysts are working with an unfamiliar event log, their primary task is to explore this log and make sense of the recorded process behavior. In exploratory process mining, this typically involves iterative cycles of inspection, filtering, and visualization aimed at revealing meaningful process patterns while managing the inherent complexity of real-life data [7]. Analysts often start by applying filters early in the exploration to focus on particular cases, activities, or time periods, thereby reducing visual clutter (e.g. by simplifying “spaghetti models”) and constructing a more interpretable process model.

However, filtering is not a neutral operation, as it actively shapes what the analyst sees. Each filtering step hides parts of the log that do not satisfy the conditions expressed in the filtering condition (also called “predicate” in this thesis), such as exceptional cases, rare paths, or incomplete traces. When multiple filters are applied sequentially, the excluded portions of data accumulate, and entire behavioral segments may disappear from the analyst’s view. This selective visibility can bias interpretations, especially when the analyst only inspects the final filtered subset. Prior studies on exploratory process mining have shown that analysts frequently move back and forth between data selection and interpretation, iteratively refining their filters as new insights emerge [8, 9]. Yet, most existing tools dynamically adapt their interface to display only the currently filtered log, offering limited awareness of what has been omitted. Making the filtered-out data visible, or at least quantifying its extent, can therefore provide valuable context, helping analysts understand whether observed patterns are representative of the overall process or artifacts of selective filtering.

This limitation can be particularly problematic in exploratory settings, where analysts often start to filter without a clear sense of which features of the log are most relevant to their analysis. Event logs frequently contain multiple levels of granularity, making it difficult to identify meaningful patterns. Existing approaches have proposed techniques to automatically highlight interesting behaviors [10, 11], but these methods rarely integrate the analyst’s evolving interests and assumptions. As filters are applied, the definition of what is “interesting” may itself shift, adding complexity to the exploration process. **Illustrative Example.** Consider the case of an analyst, hereafter referred to as Alice, who is tasked with exploring an event log from a hospital information system, loosely inspired by the sepsis event log [3]. The event log contains records of patient admissions, diagnostic tests, and treatments, but comes with minimal documentation,

leaving Alice with limited process knowledge to start with.

To reduce complexity, Alice first filters the log to include only cases in which an infection was suspected at some point during the patient’s stay. This reduces the dataset from 15,985 events across 8,956 cases to 14,147 events across 8,223 cases. She then applies a second filter, this time keeping only patients who *did not* receive an infusion, further reducing the log to 13,926 events and 6,735 cases. Although this seems like a small additional reduction, it is cumulative—cases like that of *Patient B*, already removed by the first filter, are not counted again in the second step. From Alice’s perspective, each filter appears to exclude only a small fraction of the remaining data, but in reality, the proportion of the original log being removed is much larger.

This illustrates a common challenge in process exploration: as analysts sequentially filter event logs, they gradually lose sight of the scale and nature of what is being excluded. For instance, Alice may note that a particular filter removes the 10.27% longest remaining cases, without realizing how this percentage relates to the entire original dataset. Without visibility into complementary subsets (i.e., those excluded by the filter) she cannot easily determine how filters interact, what information is being lost, or whether her assumptions about the process remain valid.

In addition, event log exploration often involves multiple perspectives that go beyond the structure of the process model itself. When Alice removes parts of the event log, the key performance indicators (KPIs) she observes—such as throughput time—can also change. After several filters, it becomes unclear which filter actually caused which change. For example, if the overall throughput time shortens after the final filter, Alice may wonder whether this is due to the last filter alone or the combined effects of multiple earlier filters. Would the same change occur if the filters were applied in a different order?

These interactions between filters make it difficult to understand how individual decisions influence the overall analysis. Without a clear overview, analysts like Alice may lose track of how their filtering choices affect both the structure and performance of the process. A framework that makes these relationships explicit could help analysts see not only what each filter does, but also how filters interact to shape the data and the resulting insights. Such a framework could also reveal what filters do not do; for instance, when analysts hold assumptions about how filters influence the data, it could help confirm or refute those assumptions.

This scenario motivates the need for methods that enable analysts to track, visualize, and interpret the effects of filtering. Such methods should not only provide insight into the retained subset but also reveal the characteristics of the excluded data, thereby ensuring greater transparency, explainability, and confidence in the exploratory process.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of sequential log filtering applied to a hospital event log. Each filter narrows the dataset further, but earlier exclusions remain hidden, hiding the full number of cases a filter would have filtered out.

1.2 Problem Statement & Research Question

In exploratory process mining, analysts often start with little prior knowledge about the structure or behavior of the event log [9]. They must explore complex relationships between different types of information, such as case attributes, event details, control-flow patterns, and time-related aspects, without a full understanding of how these factors interact.

To manage this complexity, analysts typically apply filters to focus on specific subsets of the data, such as certain case types, activity sequences, or time periods. However, every filter hides part of the original log: while the selected subset remains visible and is used for further analysis, the excluded data is often ignored. When several filters are applied in sequence, this effect compounds. Analysts usually end up examining only the final filtered subset, without seeing the intermediate stages or understanding what has been left out along the way.

As a result, important parts of the process may remain hidden, and early filtering decisions can influence how later analyses are interpreted. The underlying mechanics of this filtering process and its cumulative effects are formally described in Chapter 2.

This lack of transparency creates several problems. Analysts often make assumptions about how different filters relate to each other, but these assumptions are not always correct. For example, incomplete cases often have very short throughput times because they only capture part of the process. If these cases are removed early in the analysis, later performance results may look better than they actually are, since only the longer, complete cases remain. In this way, early filtering choices can influence everything that follows, shaping how later filters behave and possibly leading to biased or misleading conclusions.

The fundamental problem is that analysts filter event logs in order to build an understanding of it, but filtering itself requires prior understanding of the data and the effects of each filter on the data, which are understandings they do not yet possess. This creates a paradox: the analyst cannot confidently discard subsets without already knowing their significance. The absence of tools to systematically track and visualize filtering effects exacerbates this challenge, limiting both transparency and explainability.

This leads to the central research question addressed in this thesis:

How can analysts in exploratory process mining be supported in systematically tracking and visualizing the effects of sequential filtering?

1.3 Approach & Contributions

The goal of this thesis is to provide mechanisms that retain visibility into complementary subsets, support comparison across partitions, and ensure that insights remain transparent throughout the analysis process. To address this challenge, the thesis introduces a visualization framework designed to help analysts reflect more effectively on their filtering choices. The proposed solution enhances transparency by visualizing both the filters applied and the resulting subsets of data. In doing so, it draws attention not only to what has been included in the analysis but also to what has been left out. By making these distinctions visible, the framework aims to deepen analysts' understanding of their workflow, uncover patterns or assumptions that might otherwise remain implicit, and encourage a more reflective and critical engagement with the data.

The research approach draws on the principles of Design Science Research (DSR), which provides a structured methodology for developing and evaluating artifacts that address real-world problems [12]. Within this framework, the research process iteratively progresses through six stages: problem identification, definition of solution objectives, design and development of the artifact, demonstration, evaluation, and communication [13]. In this thesis, these stages are reflected respectively in the identification of limited transparency in sequential filtering (problem), the goal of enhancing interpretability and reflection (objectives), the design and implementation of the visualization framework (artifact development), its application in practical case studies (demonstration), systematic user and performance evaluations (evaluation), and the reporting of outcomes and implications in this document (communication).

Building on this methodological foundation, the thesis explores how such a framework can support reflective and exploratory analytical practices. When analysts can observe how their expectations align, or fail to align, with patterns in the data, this awareness can prompt new hypotheses and research questions. In this way, the framework contributes not only to analytical insight but also to more transparent and self-aware analysis processes.

To evaluate whether the proposed solution effectively supports analysts in the intended manner, the following evaluation questions guide the evaluation:

- **EQ1: Analytical Value:** To what extent does the framework support analysts in exploring event logs?
- **EQ2: Visualization Value:** How do users perceive aspects of the prototype, such as the usability, clarity, and interactivity?
- **EQ3: Use in Practice:** In which contexts and stages of their analytical workflow do analysts consider the tool most valuable?
- **EQ4: Algorithmic Performance:** How does the framework perform in terms of runtime and memory efficiency?

This thesis contributes to the field of exploratory process mining by introducing a new approach to systematically track and visualize the effects of sequential filtering in event log analysis. The contributions can be summarized along three main dimensions: conceptual, practical, and evaluative.

The thesis develops a conceptual framework that addresses the challenge of maintaining transparency and interpretability during sequential filtering. It formalizes how each filtering step generates both a resulting subset and a complementary subset, and how these subsets can be systematically tracked over time. Rather than treating filtered-out data as irrelevant, the framework recognizes it as a meaningful part of the analytical context that can be compared against the retained subset. This perspective introduces the idea of visualizing lineage history, capturing how each filter affects the evolving dataset.

Building on this framework, the thesis presents a prototype system that implements both tracking and visualization of sequential filters. The framework retraces each filtering step and its resulting subsets, allowing analysts to trace the evolution of the event log across multiple dimensions and metrics. Through visualization, these relationships are made explicit: analysts can see which parts of the log were excluded, how successive filters interact, and how key performance indicators (KPIs), such as throughput time, case duration, or event frequency, change over time. This visual feedback helps analysts maintain an overview of their workflow, identify interactions between filters, and detect unexpected or cumulative effects. In doing so, the approach supports analysts in understanding not only the outcomes of their filtering but also the process through which those outcomes are produced.

The evaluation investigates whether the proposed solution effectively supports analysts in the intended manner, particularly in exploring, understanding, and reflecting on their analytical steps. A user study with process analysts examined the framework's contribution to *analytical value* (**EQ1**), focusing on how the framework aids event log exploration, comprehension of filtering sequences, and the generation of new insights. Participants' feedback also provided a basis for assessing the *visualization value* (**EQ2**), highlighting strengths in usability and visual clarity, as well as opportunities for refinement in interactivity and layout design. Further, the study explored the *use in practice* (**EQ3**), identifying typical contexts in which analysts would apply the framework, such as during validation, exploratory analysis, or result presentation. Finally, demonstrations and benchmarks across multiple event logs assessed the framework's *algorithmic performance* (**EQ4**), confirming its applicability and efficiency in realistic analysis scenarios. Overall, the evaluation revealed that the framework enhances analysts' understanding of their data and analytical process, while also pointing to directions for improvement, such as expanding available metrics, improving interactivity for exploring alternative filtering paths, and enhancing scalability for longer filter sequences.

1.4 Overview

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows. Chapter 2 provides the necessary background and situates the work within the existing body of research. It introduces key concepts, formalizes the problem addressed, and reviews related work on exploratory process analysis, subset comparison, and visualization techniques for event logs. Chapter 3 outlines the proposed solution. It defines the scope and functional requirements, presents the envisioned approach, and discusses the rationale behind the chosen visualization design.

Chapter 4 describes the implementation of the prototype system. It details the core components, including lineage extraction, case-level metrics, recursive filtering, and visualization, and demonstrates the functionality on three real-world event logs: the BPIC 2017 loan application log, the Traffic Fines log, and the Sepsis log. Chapter 5 presents the evaluation of the proposed solution. It explains the design and execution of the user study, analyzes the collected data, and reports findings regarding analytical value, visualization value, and potential real-world applications, as well as the algorithmic performance of the system.

Chapter 6 discusses the results and their implications. It reflects on the proposed solution, the insights gained for analysts, its relation to existing work, and the main limitations of the research. Finally, Chapter 7 concludes the thesis and outlines directions for future research.

Chapter 2

Research Problem and Related Work

Section 2.1 presents the necessary background concepts to formally describe and understand the research problem, followed by a formal problem statement. Section 2.2 reviews existing research relevant to this thesis. It first outlines foundational work on exploratory process analysis, followed by approaches that enable subset comparison. Next, it discusses methods for multi-perspective guidance, after which it dives deeper into analyst-driven exploration, and visualization techniques. The positioning of this thesis within these research directions is discussed in Section 2.2.6

2.1 Research Problem

2.1.1 Preliminaries

In the context of process mining, an *event* refers to a single recorded occurrence of an activity within a process. Each event is associated with a set of *attributes*, such as the *activity* (i.e., the task performed), the resource involved, the outcome, and a *timestamp* indicating when the event occurred. Events are grouped into *traces*, each representing a sequence of events that belong to a specific *case*, where a case corresponds to one instance of a process and is uniquely identified by a case identifier. An *event log* L is defined as a finite set of traces, where each trace $c \in L$ is a sequence of events $c = \langle e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n \rangle$. In this thesis, the original, unfiltered event log is denoted by L^0 , representing the complete source log derived from real-world process executions.

To focus on specific behavior or reduce complexity, analysts apply *filters* based on boolean expressions known as *predicates*. A *filter* F consists of a single predicate or a conjunction of predicates $F = P_1 \wedge P_2 \wedge \dots \wedge P_k$. Evaluating a filter on a log is denoted as $\text{eval}(L, F) = L'$, where $L' \subseteq L$ contains only the traces that satisfy the filter F . The result L' is referred to as the *filtered log*, and the *complement* $\overline{L'} = L \setminus L'$ contains all traces that do not satisfy the filter.

In process mining, filters can be formulated over *event-level* or *case-level* attributes. Event-level filters operate on individual events (e.g., selecting all events performed by a specific resource or all occurrences of a given activity). By contrast, case-level filters apply to entire traces and determine whether a process instance as a whole satisfies a condition (e.g., whether a case contains at least one rejection event, or whether its duration exceeds a threshold).

In this thesis, we assume that all filters are case-level filters, meaning each filter applies to entire process instances rather than individual events. Formally, a filter f partitions L^0 into two disjoint subsets:

$$L' = \{\sigma \in L \mid f(\sigma) = \text{True}\}, \quad \overline{L'} = L \setminus L'.$$

This ensures that each case σ is either entirely included in the filtered log L' , or entirely excluded (i.e., placed in $\overline{L'}$). It is further assumed that all filters are syntactically valid, meaning they operate as intended without errors. Finally, we assume that when an analyst applies multiple filters simultaneously, these filters are motivated by a single analytical objective. In other words, the combined filter $f_1 \wedge f_2 \wedge \dots \wedge f_n$ is applied to capture a coherent analytical interest. This

assumption is important, as merging filters stemming from unrelated goals may lead to misleading or uninterpretable results in this work.

2.1.2 Problem Formalization

Let the original unfiltered event log be denoted as L^0 , where each trace $c \in L^0$ is a sequence of events $c = \langle e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n \rangle$. Each event is associated with attributes such as activity, resource, outcome, and timestamp.

A filter is defined as a Boolean predicate over traces. Applying a filter F partitions the log into two disjoint subsets:

$$\text{eval}(L^0, F) = L', \quad \overline{L'} = L^0 \setminus L',$$

where L' is the filtered log and $\overline{L'}$ is its complement. In practice, analysts typically retain only L' for further exploration, while discarding $\overline{L'}$. When multiple filters are applied sequentially,

$$F = P_1 \wedge P_2 \wedge \dots \wedge P_k,$$

the resulting subset is defined as

$$L^F = \{c \in L^0 \mid P_1(c) \wedge P_2(c) \wedge \dots \wedge P_k(c)\}.$$

This process can, in principle, partition the log into up to 2^k subsets. However, most existing tools only display the final filtered subset L^F , while intermediate partitions and their complements remain hidden (see Figure 2.1 for an example in Disco [4]).

The lack of visibility into excluded and intermediate subsets introduces several challenges. First, as filters accumulate, it becomes increasingly difficult to determine how many cases have been excluded and at which stage they were removed. Second, early filtering decisions narrow the analytical context for subsequent steps, potentially reinforcing initial assumptions. Finally, once subsets are removed, it becomes unclear how each filter alters the characteristics of the log. Some cases may satisfy multiple filter conditions, but since they are already excluded by earlier filters, the influence of their being filtered out by later filters cannot be observed. This prevents analysts from fully understanding the effects of filtering on the event log.

Figure 2.1: Example of an analysis with two sequential filters in Disco [4].

2.2 Related Work

2.2.1 Exploratory Process Analysis

Process mining focuses on analyzing real-world processes by leveraging data extracted from event logs. It includes three key types: discovery, which derives models from event logs without prior knowledge; conformance, which checks alignment between logs and existing models; and enhancement, which improves models using insights from event data, such as bottlenecks or throughput times [6]. This thesis focuses on process exploration, which often happens in combination with process discovery [14]. Especially during the early stages of process mining projects, analysts undertake various exploratory activities, such as becoming acquainted with the data to build an understanding of the underlying process, formulating or refining analytical questions, and uncovering new insights [9]. [8] further emphasize the human aspect of exploratory process mining, identifying typical analyst behaviors such as inspecting visualizations, checking assumptions, and refining questions. Their work highlights the iterative and reflective nature of process exploration.

2.2.2 Subset Comparison

The primary focus of this thesis is to support process analysts in their exploratory analysis of process data. Specifically, it aims to assist analysts in reflecting on and evaluating their own analysis activities, a concept referred to as meta-analysis. A key contribution in this area is the LogView framework [15], which supports process analysts in evaluating and comparing the results of their filters in order to validate them against expectations.

The LogView framework achieves this by characterizing result sets and comparing them with a reference log. Characterization is performed on two levels: set-level characterization, which emphasizes aggregated properties such as cardinality and attribute distributions, and element-level characterization, which focuses on individual cases. Based on these characterizations, LogView constructs intersection matrices, identifies common ancestor logs, and traces filter lineage to estimate query dependency.

What is particularly relevant about the LogView approach is its focus on comparing subsets with their source log. This aligns with the objective of this thesis, which extends comparison beyond complements by further partitioning subsets through additional filters.

Other relevant works include a web-based tool for comparing and visualizing process variants under different constraints [16], the concept of process cubes for multidimensional analysis of event data [17], multi-range query methods that allow analysts to isolate and analyze specific trace subsets [18], and the Case Group Explorer [19], an analysis approach that supports interactive grouping and comparison of event logs, while emphasizing human-guided exploration through visualization and interaction. These approaches all emphasize the importance of supporting systematic comparison between event log subsets or artifacts derived from them (e.g. visualizations) in order to improve process understanding.

2.2.3 Guidance Through Multi-Perspective Analysis

Another strand of related work focuses on guiding analysts during exploration. An example of this is ProcessExplorer [20], an interactive process mining approach designed to provide recommendations by uniting multiple process perspectives. Its guidance is based on three techniques: trace clustering to generate subset recommendations, the identification of relevant process performance indicators (PPIs), and a diversifying top- k ranking strategy to ensure variety in suggested patterns.

What makes ProcessExplorer particularly relevant to this thesis is its explicit treatment of both the control-flow and data perspectives. The control-flow perspective captures the ordering of activities and uses normalized Levenshtein edit distance to measure similarity between cases, while the data perspective applies frequent pattern mining (FPclose) to identify co-occurring attribute

sets. These are combined into a unified similarity matrix and clustered to produce meaningful subsets.

Other works also emphasize the integration of multiple perspectives. For instance, event knowledge graphs decouple process execution from a single case identifier and instead model interactions among multiple entities [21]. Methods combining control-flow and data perspectives have been proposed to improve both accuracy and interpretability of discovered models [22], while trace encoding techniques extend this by capturing both event- and trace-level attributes [23]. Clustering approaches have also been developed to simultaneously consider control-flow and data attributes for identifying distinct behaviors [24].

2.2.4 Beyond Process Mining: Analyst-Driven Exploration and Interactive Support

A further body of work emphasizes active analyst involvement. An example is Ziggy [25], which detects subspaces (views) where the user’s selection differs significantly from the rest of the dataset. Ziggy computes statistical indicators (Zig-Components) such as mean difference, frequency difference, or correlation difference, aggregates them into a Zig-Dissimilarity score, and presents the most informative views while reducing redundancy.

Ziggy is particularly relevant because it incorporates user input to define what is interesting. Instead of relying solely on data-driven patterns, it uses the user’s selection as a reference point, surfacing insights that are both novel and personally meaningful. This closely aligns with the methodology of this thesis, which builds on user-defined filters to partition event logs and compare subsets in layered, multi-faceted ways.

Other systems similarly emphasize interactivity and user intent. For example, [26] proposes iterative systems that adapt to user input by revealing divergences between current and background data distributions. [27] introduces a principled architecture for interactive, user-driven exploration, while [28] stresses the need to design systems that accommodate the evolving objectives of analysts over time.

2.2.5 Beyond Process Mining: Visualization Techniques

Several works have explored how event log data can be visualized. Four studies are especially relevant for this thesis, as they propose different strategies for representing logs.

The first is [17], which introduced the idea of process cubes. A process cube is a multidimensional representation of an event log, where cases can be sliced along dimensions such as time, organizational unit, or case attributes. By splitting the cube, analysts can compare subsets across dimensions, for example contrasting cohorts of students or departments within an organization. This work was an inspiration for the approach in this thesis, as it shows how visual structuring can support comparisons. The difference is that process cubes focus on cross-dimensional slicing, while this thesis focuses on the lineage of sequential filters applied by the analyst.

Building on this concept, [29] demonstrated how process cubes can be applied in practice through a case study. They analyzed logs of students watching recorded lectures and taking exams, slicing cubes along dimensions such as gender, nationality, or course instances to reveal study patterns and performance differences. Each cube cell was characterized with simple metrics such as the number of students, average events per student, views per student, exams per student, and trace fitness with respect to a reference model. This showed how quantitative descriptors can make subsets directly comparable beyond their discovered control-flow. This thesis adopts a similar logic but replaces cross-dimensional slicing with the sequential filters chosen by the analyst. Each filter step produces a subset that can likewise be characterized with metrics.

The third study [30], introduces techniques for presenting process data as it unfolds. They evaluate timelines, heatmaps, and flow-based representations that help detect deviations and bottlenecks. While these methods do not partition logs through filtering, they demonstrate the value of clear visual encodings for making patterns in process data interpretable.

The fourth study [31], proposes grouping cases into variants based on partial orders rather than strict sequences. They show how variants can be visualized both in aggregate and at the level of individual traces, allowing analysts to move between different granularities. This relates to one of the goals of this thesis, which is to make visible the event log and the analysis on different levels of granularity.

Recent advancements have further emphasized the convergence between Process Mining (PM) and Visual Analytics (VA). Van den Elzen et al. [32] present a systematic exploration of multi-faceted visual process analytics (VPA), identifying how PM can benefit from established VA principles for handling complex data facets. The Dagstuhl Seminar Report Human in the (Process) Mines [33] underscores the growing importance of human-centered approaches in PM, introducing knowledge-assisted interactive frameworks that situate analysts within the analytical feedback loop. Moreover, the visualization of multi-faceted and overlapping event structures in PM can benefit from advances in set visualization techniques as surveyed by [34], who classify state-of-the-art visual methods for representing set relations and propose guidelines for designing scalable and interpretable multi-set visualizations.

2.2.6 Positioning of this Thesis

The work presented in this thesis builds upon and extends several research directions discussed above. From exploratory process analysis, it adopts the understanding of analysis as an iterative and reflective activity [9, 8], emphasizing the analyst’s role in shaping insights through exploration. From subset comparison approaches such as LogView [15], it inherits the concept of tracking and characterizing subsets of an event log to assess their properties. This thesis extends that foundation by visualizing not only the resulting subsets, but also their complements and the full lineage of filters applied over time.

Furthermore, while tools such as ProcessExplorer [20] and the Case Group Explorer [19] provide guidance and interactive grouping, they primarily focus on automatic or user-defined clustering at a single stage of the analysis. The present work supports a similar reflection on the sequence of analyst-defined filters, enabling users to trace how earlier decisions shape later results and to revisit those decisions in context.

From a visualization standpoint, the proposed framework extends concepts from process cubes [17, 29] and related log visualization methods [30, 31]. Whereas process cubes enable cross-sectional comparison along static dimensions, this thesis introduces a similar approach, but in which the analyst’s own filter sequence defines the structure of comparison. By linking subsets and their complements through shared metrics and visual encodings, the framework makes the filtering lineage of the log explicit across multiple perspectives.

In summary, this thesis integrates ideas from subset comparison, multi-perspective guidance, and interactive visualization into a framework for exploratory process analysis. Its novelty lies in: (i) explicitly visualizing both retained and excluded subsets across sequential filters; (ii) connecting these subsets through a lineage-aware structure that preserves analytical history; and (iii) demonstrating, through a prototype and user study, how such a framework can support understanding, reflection, and insight generation into an exploratory analysis.

Chapter 3

Approach

This chapter describes the development of the framework, outlining how the concept evolved from problem exploration to the final design.

Section 3.1 defines the scope and boundaries of this work, clarifying the type of event logs, filtering mechanisms, and user perspectives considered. Section 3.2 introduces the problem investigation and design rationale. It explains how the idea of including complementary subsets emerged from early conceptual sketches and how this insight led to the formulation of a framework for tracking and comparing multiple filtering paths. Finally, Section 3.3 discusses the selection of the chart type.

3.1 Scope

The scope of this thesis is defined along several dimensions. First, the concept developed focuses on a limited set of metrics that are typically available in most event logs. The implementation assumes that the log contains timestamps, well-defined cases and events, as well as attributes suitable for filtering and for the computation of metrics. Within this context, the thesis is scoped to sequential case filters, meaning that filters either include or exclude entire cases rather than individual events. Consequently, the dataset is always partitioned into two subsets: the cases that pass the filter and those that do not.

Second, the thesis is oriented toward the needs of process analysts. The forthcoming visualization approach is intended to be understandable and useful for individuals with at least some experience in process analytics and filtering. The intended audience does not include stakeholders or users without prior knowledge of process analytics, and the thesis does not aim to evaluate visualization as a communication tool for non-analysts.

Third, the focus of this work lies on conceptual and cognitive aspects of the framework rather than on technical optimization. While basic performance testing is carried out, issues such as scalability, efficiency, or integration into broader toolchains fall outside the primary scope. The framework is intended to support process exploration rather than modeling, prediction, or aggregation, and they do not aim to provide causal explanations. Instead, they are designed to facilitate sense-making by deepening analysts' understanding of their analysis steps, rather than to produce definitive analytical results.

Fourth, the evaluation of the forthcoming approach is exploratory in nature. The aim is to examine how the concept can be improved and to gather insights into its potential usefulness, rather than to conduct comparative studies against existing tools. The thesis assumes that sequential filtering is representative of at least part of the exploratory process analysis workflow, and any implementation developed as part of this work should be regarded as a proof of concept rather than a production-ready system.

Finally, this thesis should be understood as a first step toward a broader research direction. The present scope is deliberately narrow in order to establish the foundations of the approach.

Future work is expected to extend the coverage to additional metrics, more complex filtering mechanisms, and other types of analytical interactions.

3.2 Problem Investigation and Design

The development of the framework began with a conceptual sketch of the problem. As illustrated in Figure 3.1a, when filters are applied sequentially to an event log—that is, when each new filter operates on an already filtered subset—a portion of data is progressively excluded. With each additional filter, the total share of discarded data increases. However, these excluded subsets may still contain valuable information that can be leveraged to compare the filtered result set against the original dataset.

From this observation, the idea emerged to apply the same filters not only to the main log L , but also to its complements. For instance, instead of discarding complement C_1 , we can apply the same filter used on L' to C_1 as well. This allows us to assess whether the filter has a similar effect on the complement, for example in terms of the percentage of cases filtered in or out.

As shown in Figure 3.1b, applying filters F_1 to F_3 sequentially results in progressively smaller subsets along the main (blue) path. However, if we continue applying the same filters to both the filtered-in and filtered-out subsets, we obtain 2^F result sets after F filters. For instance, after three filters this produces $2^3 = 8$ subsets, offering a richer view of how the filters partition the original dataset.

(a) Sequential filtering excludes complementary subsets.

(b) Applying filters to both subsets yields 2^F result sets.

Figure 3.1: Conceptual sketches illustrating (a) the exclusion of complementary subsets and (b) the resulting partitioning of the log through repeated filtering.

Beyond comparing inclusion and exclusion percentages, additional insight can be obtained by examining case-level metrics, such as case duration. This enables the analyst to detect whether filters have similar or differing effects on the resulting subsets. Figure 3.2 illustrates two scenarios: in the first, filters behave independently, while in the second, the first filter affects the outcome of the next.

The goal was to characterize the subsets and filtering paths in a way that would be both informative and comprehensible for the analyst. Since the framework is designed for exploratory use by process analysts, it is assumed that users possess general expertise in process analysis but may lack detailed knowledge about the specific event log under study.

Figure 3.2: Comparison of filtering behavior based on case duration (in days). In (a), the first filter does not influence the effect of the second; both subsets show similar trends in case duration. In (b), the first filter modifies how the second affects duration. Cases that passed the first filter react differently than those that did not.

To ensure broad applicability, the characterization focuses on aspects common to virtually all event logs: timestamps, events, and cases. From this consideration, a set of metrics was defined for the first prototype: number of cases, average case duration, average number of events per case, and average time between events. These metrics provide a simple yet meaningful basis for comparing different filtering paths.

Furthermore, the prototype was designed to highlight distinct filtering paths to make relevant comparisons more apparent. For example, in Figure 3.3, the main path representing the analyst's typical filtering sequence is highlighted in blue, while the alternative path that uses the complement of the first filter (but applies the same second and third filters) is highlighted in pink. This framework clearly illustrates how the sequence of filters influences the final outcome.

Figure 3.3: Final sketch of the envisioned solution, based on the BPIC 2017 event log [1]. The figure illustrates three sequential filters: (1) division of cases by variant frequency (high- vs. low-frequency variants), (2) separation of cases with two or more loan offers from those with fewer, and (3) distinction between successful cases (ending with **Pending**) and unsuccessful ones.

3.3 Choice of the Chart Type

To ground the design in analysts needs, a survey was distributed among participants with knowledge of process mining ($n = 9$). The survey first explained the problem context and then presented several visualizations, including a Sankey diagram, a Sunburst chart, an Icicle chart, and a Tree chart (see Figure 3.4). Participants were asked to interpret these visuals, reflect on their strengths and weaknesses, and respond to open-ended questions about functional requirements for supporting process analysts in exploratory tasks.

The results indicated a clear preference for the Icicle chart, which was considered both the most useful and the chart participants would be most likely to use in practice. The open-ended responses highlighted several features to improve analytical support: a combination of flow (as in Sankey diagrams) with hierarchical splits (as in Icicle plots), the addition of interactivity (e.g., reordering filters), zooming into small subsets, showing exact values alongside color encodings, displaying group sizes, and providing more details such as the number of cases or the impact of filter order on outcomes.

Figure 3.4: Chart types presented in the survey: (a) sunburst, (b) Sankey, (c) tree, and (d) icicle charts.

Chapter 4

Implementation & Demonstration

This chapter describes the implementation of the framework and its application to real-world event logs. Section 4.1 outlines the overall workflow, Section 4.2 details the core components, and Section 4.3 demonstrates the framework on benchmark datasets. The implementation is available at: ¹ [35].

4.1 Overview

The overall workflow consists of four main stages: (1) extracting the filter lineage, (2) applying filters to this lineage, (3) enriching the data with case-level metrics, and (4) producing visualizations. This pipeline is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: End-to-End Workflow

Input: Result set identifier r , log view V , metric m

Output: Interactive visualization

$L \leftarrow \text{get_lineage}(V, r);$

$S \leftarrow \text{apply_filters}(L, V, m);$

enrich S with case-level features;

aggregate statistics per subset;

visualize(S , method={icicle, pie});

These functions are built on top of the LogView framework [15], specifically its Query Registry component. LogView supports exploratory case filtering and comparative process analysis by providing an interface for interactively applying and tracking filtering queries on event logs. Each query execution is recorded in the registry, which maintains the full context of every filtering step. This enables complete lineage tracking, allowing each result set to be traced back to its origin through a clearly defined sequence of filters.

4.2 Implementation of Core Functions

4.2.1 Lineage Extraction

The first step is to reconstruct the lineage of a result set. This allows analysts to get insight into how a particular subset was produced by iteratively applying filters. The algorithm traverses the registry backwards until it reaches the original source log, and then reverses the order to show the lineage in forward direction.

¹<https://github.com/lauradidden/Sequential-Filtering-Visualization>

Algorithm 2: Lineage Extraction (`get_lineage()`)

Input: Registry of evaluations E , result set identifier r
Output: Lineage dataframe L
 $L \leftarrow \emptyset$;
`trace_back(r)` **foreach** $row \in E$ **do**
 if $row.result_set = r$ **then**
 append row to L ;
 `trace_back($row.source_log$)`;
`trace_back(r)`;
return $reverse(L)$;

4.2.2 Case-Level Metrics

To make subsets comparable, three case-level metrics are computed for each trace: (1) the case duration, (2) the number of events per case, and (3) the average time between consecutive events. These metrics are simple yet informative, and are available in almost any event log.

The first algorithm computes the duration of each case as the time difference between the first and last event:

Algorithm 3: Case Duration Computation (`add_case_durations()`)

Input: Event log D
Output: Case duration per case $duration(c)$
foreach $case\ c \in D$ **do**
 $duration(c) \leftarrow \max(time(c)) - \min(time(c))$;
 attach $duration(c)$ to all events of c ;

The second algorithm counts the number of events associated with each case:

Algorithm 4: Event Count Computation (`add_event_counts()`)

Input: Event log D
Output: Number of events per case $num_events(c)$
foreach $case\ c \in D$ **do**
 $num_events(c) \leftarrow |events(c)|$;
 attach $num_events(c)$ to all events of c ;

Finally, the third metric measures the average time between consecutive events, providing an indication of process tempo:

Algorithm 5: Average Time Between Events (`add_avg_time_between_events()`)

Input: Event log D
Output: Average inter-event time per case $avg(c)$
foreach $case\ c \in D$ **do**
 sort events of c by timestamp;
 $diffs \leftarrow$ successive time differences;
 $avg(c) \leftarrow mean(diffs)$;
 attach $avg(c)$ to all events of c ;

At present, three metrics are implemented, and no functionality is yet provided for analysts to define custom metrics directly. To add a new metric, a developer must implement a function that takes an event log as input, computes the metric at the case level, and appends the resulting values as a new attribute to all events belonging to each corresponding case.

4.2.3 Applying Filters

The filtering procedure applies each filter in sequence, splitting the log into a filtered subset and its complement. For each resulting subset, statistics are computed according to the chosen metric. After F filters, this yields up to 2^F subsets, which together provide a complete partitioning of the original log.

Algorithm 6: Applying Filters (`apply_filters()`)

Input: Initial log L , sequence of queries Q , metric m

Output: Set of subsets S with statistics

$S \leftarrow \{L\}$;

for $q \in Q$ **do**

$S' \leftarrow \emptyset$;

foreach subset $s \in S$ **do**

$(s_f, s_c) \leftarrow \text{evaluate}(s, q)$;

 compute statistics(s_f, m);

 compute statistics(s_c, m);

 add s_f, s_c to S' ;

$S \leftarrow S'$;

return S ;

4.2.4 Visualization

The final component generates visualizations. Two complementary visualizations are supported:

Icicle chart: displays subsets in a hierarchical structure, highlighting the main filtering path while showing metric values with a color scale.

Algorithm 7: Icicle Chart Generation (`query_exploration_icicle()`)

Input: Result set r , log view V , metric m

Output: Interactive icicle chart

$L \leftarrow \text{get_lineage}(V, r)$;

$S \leftarrow \text{apply_filters}(L, V, m)$;

augment S with labels and colors;

plot icicle diagram using Plotly;

Pie chart: focuses on the final filtering step, comparing sibling subsets and their metric distributions.

Algorithm 8: Pie Chart Generation (`query_breakdown_pie()`)

Input: Result set identifier r , log view V , metric m

Output: Interactive pie chart of subsets

$L \leftarrow \text{get_lineage}(V, r)$;

$S \leftarrow \text{apply_filters}(L, V, m)$;

$siblings \leftarrow \text{get_sibling_subsets}(S, r)$;

foreach subset $s \in siblings$ **do**

 compute mean(m) for s ;

 assign color according to metric type;

plot pie chart using Plotly;

4.3 Demonstration

The code components described above are integrated into a Python library, `filter_visualizations`. This library provides a simple way to call the visualizations directly from a result set.

For example, the Icicle chart can be generated with:

```
icicle(result_set_name, log_view, metric="metric_name", details=True)
```

Similarly, the Pie chart focusing on the final filtering step can be produced with:

```
pie(result_set_name, log_view, metric="avg_case_duration_seconds", details=True)
```

4.3.1 BPI Challenge 2017 Log

The first demonstration focuses on the *BPI Challenge 2017 Log* [1], which documents the end-to-end handling of loan applications at a Dutch financial institution. Each case represents a single loan request, covering activities such as application creation, credit assessment, and loan approval. The log includes several numerical and categorical attributes, including the applicant's credit score, requested loan amount, application type, and timestamps. This analysis examines how a predefined sequence of filters progressively shapes the resulting dataset. The goal is to understand how filtering alters process metrics such as duration and structural complexity, and how much information is lost when focusing only on the final subset, as is common in conventional process mining tools.

The applied filters are summarized in Table 4.1. Starting from the full log (`initial_source_log`), each predicate produces a refined subset, ending with `rs_ModerateDuration`, which represents the final resulting dataset that would typically be shown in isolation in existing tools.

Table 4.1: Filters applied in the BPI 2017 Log, with their context.

Predicate	Description (Application Context and Purpose)
<code>(CreditScore ≥ 600)</code>	Applied to the full log to isolate reliable applicants with sufficient credit scores; serves as the foundation for subsequent filtering (Figs. 4.1–4.2).
<code>(RequestedAmount ≥ 10000)</code>	Applied to the good-credit subset to focus on larger loan requests that usually require more extensive review and verification.
<code>(RequestedAmount < 15000)</code>	Narrows the sample to mid-range loans by excluding extreme high-value cases, stabilizing performance indicators.
<code>(ApplicationType ∈ {New credit})</code>	Retains only new loan applications, excluding renewals or extensions to ensure consistent process structure.

To assess how sequential filtering affects process characteristics, three visual perspectives were considered: (1) changes in the average number of events per case, (2) changes in average case duration, and (3) the relative size of retained and discarded subsets after the last filter.

The first visualization (Fig. 4.1) shows the average number of events per case for each intermediate subset. A clear pattern emerges: after applying the first filter (`CreditScore ≥ 600`), the average number of events per case increases notably. This suggests that applicants with higher credit scores follow more structured processes involving additional, often automated, steps that do not prolong case handling.

Figure 4.2 tracks the evolution of average case duration across the same filter sequence. Interestingly, the first filter shows an inverse relationship between the number of events and case duration: high-credit applicants experience shorter overall case durations despite having more events. In later steps, both duration and event count tend to increase/decrease together..

The third visualization (Fig. 4.3) compares the proportion of cases retained and discarded after the last filter using pie charts. This perspective reveals that the final subset (`rs_ModerateDuration`) represents only a small fraction of the original data. Most cases are excluded at intermediate steps, meaning that conventional analyses, typically performed on the final subset alone, overlook a large

Figure 4.1: Average number of events per case across sequential filtering steps in the BPI 2017 Loan Application Log.

Figure 4.2: Average case duration across sequential filtering steps in the BPI 2017 Loan Application Log.

part of the process. These discarded subsets may still contain valuable insights, such as atypical loan-handling paths.

Figure 4.3: Proportion of retained and discarded subsets after each filter in the BPI 2017 meta-analysis.

4.3.2 Road Traffic Fine Management Process Log

The second demonstration focuses on the *Road Traffic Fine Management Process Log* [2], a benchmark dataset containing real-world cases of traffic fine management. This analysis illustrates how the approach enables understanding of process behavior through comparative inspection. The analysis was structured around four main aspects: (A) the relation between the activities **Send for Credit Collection** and **Payment**, (B) the meaning of predefined **Variant** labels, (C) performance changes before and after 2006, and (D) long-duration cases.

Table 4.2 summarizes all filters used throughout the analysis, including their application context and analytical purpose.

A. Credit Collection and Payment Relationship

The first step aimed to examine whether cases sent for credit collection (SCC) were subsequently paid, and how these unpaid cases differ from the overall log behavior. To this end, the full Traffic Fines Log was filtered to select cases containing the activity **Send for Credit Collection** and to exclude those containing **Payment**.

The icicle visualization was used on this subset to display the average number of events per case. This visualization (Fig. 4.4) highlights the behavioral separation between paid and unpaid fines, revealing that unpaid SCC cases tend to have more events per case.

Table 4.2: Filters applied in the Traffic Fines Log analysis, with their context and rationale.

Predicate	Description (Application Context and Purpose)
$(\text{Activity} \in \{\text{Send for Credit Collection}\})$	Applied to the full Traffic Fines Log to isolate all cases involving the initiation of credit collection; used as a foundation for overlap analysis in Fig. 4.4.
$(\text{Activity} \notin \{\text{Payment}\})$	Applied to <code>rs_SCC</code> to form <code>rs_SCC_and_no_Payment_2</code> ; used to focus on unpaid fines and assess their structure relative to the rest of the log.
$(\text{Variant} \in \{\text{Variant 1, Variant 2, Variant 3}\})$	Applied to <code>rs_SCC_and_no_Payment_2</code> to explore variant-specific behaviors and compare their structural complexity (Fig. 4.5).
$(\text{Complete Timestamp} \leq 2006-01-01 00:00:00)$	Applied to <code>rs_SCC_and_no_Payment_2</code> to study temporal differences before and after 2006 (Fig. 4.6).
$(\text{DurationWithin } [50\text{M}, 80\text{M}])$	Applied to the full log to focus on the longest cases, followed by <code>SCC</code> and <code>Payment</code> filters to derive <code>rs_duration_credit_no_payment</code> (Fig. 4.7).

Figure 4.4: Icicle visualization of unpaid SCC cases compared with the full Traffic Fines Log.

B. Analysis of Process Variants

Next, the analysis focused on understanding whether the dataset’s predefined `Variant` labels correspond to meaningful behavioral distinctions in the unpaid `SCC` subset. Three variant-based subsets were created from `rs_SCC_and_no_Payment_2`: one each for `Variant 1`, `Variant 2`, and `Variant 3`. Each subset was visualized using an icicle chart to compare process complexity and duration. (Fig. 4.5) shows the icicle chart with a filter for `Variant 2`.

The comparison suggests that `Variant 1` primarily represents unpaid `SCC` cases, whereas `Variant 2` represents mostly cases with payment activities. `Variant 3` captures less frequent behavior, representing neither `SCC` nor payment activity. These findings indicate that while the variant labels partially align with observed patterns, their definitions likely depend on additional attributes not captured in the visible activity log.

C. Case Duration Before and After 2006

Given that the dataset spans more than a decade, a temporal filter was applied to assess the case duration over time. Cases completed on or before January 1, 2006, were isolated from `rs_SCC_and_no_Payment_2` to form the subset `rs_SCC_before_2006`. The icicle visualization

Figure 4.5: Variant-level icicles within the unpaid SCC subset.

for this subset (Fig. 4.6) revealed a clear increase in case duration after 2006, particularly for SCC-related paths. Interestingly, the presence or absence of payment did not significantly alter this trend, suggesting an decrease in process efficiency.

Figure 4.6: Icicle visualization of unpaid SCC cases completed before 2006.

D. Long-Duration Case Analysis

Finally, the analysis focused on cases with long durations. A duration filter was applied to select cases lasting between 50 and 80 million seconds (approximately 1.6–2.5 years), forming the subset `rs_duration`. From this, cases including SCC but excluding Payment were extracted as `rs_duration_credit_no_payment`. The corresponding icicle visualization (Fig. 4.7) shows that long-duration cases often involve more events per case, consistent with the more complex, possibly unresolved fines.

Figure 4.7: Icicle visualization of long-duration unpaid SCC cases.

4.3.3 Sepsis Cases Event Log

The third demonstration applies the approach to the *Sepsis Cases Event Log* [3], which records clinical pathways of patients suspected of sepsis. Each case represents an individual patient’s trajectory through the hospital, including diagnostic, treatment, and admission events. The dataset contains approximately 1,000 cases with 15,000 events across 16 activities, along with 39 attributes such as laboratory results, age, and diagnostic indicators.

The analyses aimed to identify how clinical and demographic factors affect process structure. Three main aspects were examined: (A) elderly patient treatment patterns, (B) infection-related processes, and (C) ICU admissions. Each analysis used an icicle visualization to explore the structural characteristics and performance of filtered subsets. Table 4.3 summarizes the filters applied in this analysis, and their analytical role.

A. Elderly Patients and Treatment Patterns

The first analysis explored whether elderly patients ($\text{Age} \geq 65$) exhibited longer stays and more complex care trajectories. The full Sepsis Log was first filtered to isolate elderly patients, then refined to include those who received intravenous (IV) antibiotics ($\text{Activity} \in \{\text{IV Antibiotics}\}$), and finally those who also underwent a chest X-ray ($\text{DiagnosticXthorax} = \text{True}$). The resulting subset, `rs_Elderly_with_Antibiotics_and_XRay`, represents elderly patients who received both antibiotic therapy and diagnostic imaging.

Figure 4.8 shows the icicle visualization with the average number of events per case. As expected, elderly patients generally had longer ER stays than younger ones. However, receiving IV antibiotics substantially increased both duration and number of activities per case, reflecting higher treatment complexity. In contrast, having an X-ray did not significantly affect stay length, suggesting that imaging was a standard, efficiently integrated diagnostic step.

B. Infection-Related Processes

The second analysis examined how infection suspicion and related interventions influenced treatment duration. The log was filtered to include patients flagged as having a suspected infection ($\text{InfectionSuspected} = \text{True}$), then refined to those who received blood diagnostics ($\text{DiagnosticBlood} = \text{True}$) and further to those who also received an infusion treatment ($\text{Infusion} = \text{True}$). The final sub-

Table 4.3: Filters applied in the Sepsis Log analysis, with their context and rationale.

Predicate	Description (Application Context and Purpose)
(Age ≥ 65)	Applied to the full Sepsis Log to isolate elderly patients and compare their process durations and activity counts with younger patients (Fig. 4.8).
(Activity ∈ {IV Antibiotics})	Applied to elderly patients to examine the effect of intravenous antibiotic treatment on stay length and process complexity (Fig. 4.8).
(DiagnosticXthorax = True)	Applied to elderly patients who received antibiotics, to assess whether diagnostic imaging further affected duration (Fig. 4.8).
(InfectionSuspected = True)	Applied to the full log to explore the relationship between infection suspicion and treatment intensity (Fig. 4.9).
(DiagnosticBlood = True)	Applied to suspected infection cases to investigate how blood diagnostics align with infection suspicion (Fig. 4.9).
(Infusion = True)	Applied to infection cases with blood diagnostics to assess whether infusion treatment influences hospitalization time (Fig. 4.9).
(Activity ∈ {Admission IC})	Applied to the full log to identify ICU admissions and study critical care pathways (Fig. 4.10).
(CRP ≥ 100)	Applied to ICU admissions to isolate patients with high inflammatory responses and examine severity-related behavior (Fig. 4.10).
(Activity ∈ {IV Antibiotics})	Applied to ICU cases with elevated CRP levels to compare outcomes of antibiotic treatment versus no treatment (Fig. 4.10).

Figure 4.8: Icicle visualization of elderly patients receiving IV antibiotics and chest X-rays.

set, `rs_Infection_with_BloodDiagnostic_and_Infusion`, thus represents the most severe and resource-intensive cases.

The icicle visualization in Fig. 4.9 shows the average time between events as a metric. The visualizations highlight that these three attributes tend to co-occur. Patients with a suspected infection who did not undergo blood diagnostics showed extreme differences depending on infusion treatment: those who received infusions stayed over 80 days on average, compared to 9 days for those who did not. A similar pattern is visible in for the average time between events (Fig. 4.9). The relatively similar number of events per case suggests that the longer duration was driven by slower progression rather than additional activity.

Figure 4.9: Icicle visualization of patients with suspected infection, blood diagnostics, and infusion treatments.

C. ICU Admissions and Clinical Severity

The third analysis focused on patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) and explored the relation between severity markers and treatment. A filter selecting cases with ICU admission events ($\text{Activity} \in \{\text{Admission IC}\}$) was applied to the full log, forming `rs_Admission_IC`. Within this subset, two additional filters were introduced: one selecting cases with elevated C-reactive protein levels ($\text{CRP} \geq 100$), a marker of severe infection, and another selecting cases where IV antibiotics were administered ($\text{Activity} \in \{\text{IV Antibiotics}\}$). The resulting subset, `rs_ICU_HighCRP_with_Antibiotics`, represents severe sepsis cases requiring both intensive care and antibiotic treatment.

As shown in Fig. 4.10, ICU admissions form a relatively small subset of the log but are characterized by substantially longer durations. High CRP values strongly correlated with ICU admission and antibiotic use. Among ICU patients with lower CRP levels, those who received antibiotics had shorter stays, while those who did not had markedly longer durations. This may indicate that antibiotic intervention reduced complications in less severe cases, though further medical interpretation would be needed to confirm this.

Figure 4.10: Icicle visualization of ICU admissions with high CRP values and antibiotic treatment.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

This chapter presents the evaluation of the proposed framework. Section 5.1 outlines the design of the user study, including its objectives, evaluation questions, and inclusion criteria. Section 5.2 then describes the execution of the study, detailing the preparation, procedure, and data collection methods used. Section 5.3 explains how both quantitative and qualitative data were analyzed to evaluate the prototype, while Section 5.4 presents the resulting findings regarding analytical value, visualization value, and potential use in practice. Finally, Section 5.5 reports on the algorithmic performance of the framework, focusing on runtime and memory efficiency across different datasets.

5.1 User Study: Design

The objective of the user study is to assess the framework with respect to its *analytical value*, *visualization value*, and *practical applicability*. Accordingly, three of the four evaluation questions introduced in Section 1.3 are addressed through the user study, while the fourth (EQ4: Algorithmic Performance) is examined separately in Section 5.5. The study was structured to evaluate both analytical and experiential aspects of the framework through a supervised analysis task using a real-world event log [1]. Multiple data collection methods were combined to ensure comprehensive coverage of the evaluation objectives.

- **EQ1: Analytical Value:** To what extent does the framework support analysts in exploring event logs? This question was addressed through a *think-aloud protocol* during task execution, allowing participants to verbalize their reasoning, discoveries, and reflections in real time. These verbal protocols were later analyzed thematically to identify how the framework contributed to exploration, insight generation, and understanding of sequential filtering steps.
- **EQ2: Visualization Value:** How do users perceive implementation aspects of the visualization, such as its usability, clarity, and interactivity? This aspect was assessed primarily through the *ICE-T questionnaire* [36], which measures perceived Insight, Confidence, Essence, and Time efficiency on a 7-point Likert scale. Qualitative feedback provided during and after questionnaire completion further contextualized these quantitative ratings, highlighting both strengths and challenges in usability, visual clarity, and interaction design.
- **EQ3: Use in Practice:** In which contexts and stages of their analytical workflow do analysts consider the framework most valuable? This question was explored through *semi-structured interview questions* following the task, focusing on when and how participants envisioned using the framework in their analytical workflows, and in what types of real-world projects or scenarios it would provide added value.

An overview of the user study design is shown in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Overview of the user study design.

The target group consisted of process analysts from both academia and industry, particularly those engaged in exploratory data analysis. Participants were selected based on the following inclusion criteria: familiarity with Python and Jupyter notebooks (**IC1**); prior experience with filtering using the `pm4py` library (**IC2**); and hands-on experience with event log exploration (**IC3**). Additionally, participants were required to be able to analyze event logs independently, without external support from process mining experts (**IC4**). All criteria were verified through the demographic questionnaire (see Appendix A).

The evaluation session consisted of a supervised analysis task, where the participants had to answer one of the following questions about the BPI Challenge 2017 event log [1]:

1. Do high-value new applications that end in successful loan approval tend to follow longer or more complex processes than those that do not?
2. Do in-person submitted applications for car loans behave differently from digital submissions, particularly when the requested amount exceeds €5,000?

These questions were selected to direct participants toward specific filters that kept the analyses feasible within the allocated timeframe and allowed for the provision of efficient support when needed. At the same time, the task deliberately left open which metrics should be applied, since concepts such as “complexity” and “performance” may be interpreted differently. This served as an implicit test of whether the framework exposes suitable metrics. Offering two possible questions also provided flexibility in case one was perceived as difficult by a participant. A complete solution to both questions was also prepared, to be used in case the participant did not reach the stage of using the framework, or if they used it incorrectly.

Two complementary evaluation methods were employed to collect feedback from the participants. First, the ICE-T questionnaire [36] was used (see Appendix B). This questionnaire measures four dimensions: insight, confidence, essence, and time. ICE-T is a heuristic framework designed to capture broad, value-centric aspects of framework use, rather than relying on task-specific performance metrics [36]. The numerical ratings provide a structured overview of how well the framework performed on aspects it was designed to support, and highlight areas requiring further refinement. This enabled a quantitative assessment of the framework.

Second, qualitative feedback was collected. This was done by collecting the think-aloud during task execution, open-ended interview questions following the task, and comments provided while completing the ICE-T questionnaire. These data complement the quantitative results by capturing participant reasoning, identifying specific features that supported or hindered analysis, and revealing points of confusion.

The additional open-ended questions were grouped into two thematic categories to complement the quantitative measures and think-aloud data.

- Q1: Implementation of the Approach: These questions focused on evaluating how participants perceived the functionality and usability of the prototype.
 - Q1a: Which features of the framework were most informative, and which were not?
 - Q1b: Which additional features would better support analysis?
- Q2: Use in Practice: These questions focused on how participants envisioned applying the framework in real-world analytical contexts.

- Q2a: At which points during your analysis process would you consider using these functions, and why?
- Q2b: Can you describe a real-world task or project where this framework would be useful, and how you would integrate it into your workflow?

5.1.1 Demographics

The study involved nine participants. An additional participant with whom a pilot evaluation was performed was excluded from the final analysis. Seven were aged between 25–34 years, and two between 35–44 years. In terms of expertise, participants ranged from *Basic* (2) and *Average* (2) to *Good* (3) and *Advanced* (2), with an average of about 4 years of process mining experience. Most participants had participated in 2–3 projects in the past three years, though one reported a single project and another more than five. All but one had used the `pm4py` library before.

Figure 5.2 presents an overview of the participant demographics in terms of process mining expertise, current job title, native language, and country of residence.

Figure 5.2: Demographic distribution of participants across (a) process mining expertise, (b) current job title, (c) native language, and (d) country of residence.

5.2 User Study: Execution

Prior to the study sessions, participants were asked to complete three preparatory steps: review a tutorial notebook, sign a consent form, and complete a demographic survey.

The framework builds on the LogView framework by using its registry to track the lineage of subsets and its filter-application functionality to define filters. Accordingly, the tutorial notebook introduced the LogView framework, demonstrated how to define filters using `pm4py`, and explained how to generate and interpret the resulting visualizations.

This ensured that participants had the necessary background to perform the evaluation tasks. Part of the tutorial notebook are shown in 5.3. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the study was reviewed and approved on 09-07-2025 by the Ethical Review Committee of Eindhoven University of Technology. The demographic survey verified the inclusion criteria (ICs) described earlier.

Each testing session lasted approximately one hour and was both screen- and audio-recorded. Participants were first given 30 minutes to complete one of the analysis tasks independently, while being allowed to use the tutorial notebook as guidance. During this phase, they were asked to think aloud [37], allowing their reasoning, difficulties, and perceptions of the framework to be captured in real time. Part of the testing notebook are shown in 5.4.

After completing the task, participants filled out the ICE-T questionnaire [36], again using a think-aloud protocol to elaborate on their ratings. This was followed by the open-ended questions listed in Section 6.1. Finally, participants were asked whether they had any additional feedback. The session then concluded, and participants were thanked for their time and contribution.

`query_exploration_icicle()` Function Parameters

Parameter	Type	Description
<code>result_set_name</code>	<code>str</code>	The name of the result set you want to visualize. This must match the name used when calling <code>log_view.evaluate_query(...)</code> . Any name in the list of "result_set" names can be used to call the function.
<code>log_view</code>	<code>LogView</code>	A <code>LogView</code> object that stores the original event log along with all filtering steps applied. Created using <code>LogViewBuilder.build_log_view(log)</code> .
<code>metric</code>	<code>str</code>	The metric to visualize in the chart. Supported options: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <code>"avg_case_duration_seconds"</code> (default) <code>"avg_events_per_case"</code> <code>"avg_time_between_events"</code>
<code>show_time</code>	<code>bool</code>	If <code>True</code> , prints the time taken for each internal step (lineage extraction, filtering, plotting). Default is <code>False</code> .
<code>details</code>	<code>bool</code>	If <code>True</code> (default), prints a summary showing all filter steps, number of cases per subset, and computed metric values.

Intended Use:

- Get a visual understanding of how filters affect your dataset.
- Identify which branches of the filtering tree are interesting or potentially problematic.
- Validate your filtering logic and observe how metrics change across subsets.
- Clearly communicate your data preparation and filtering steps.

The `query_exploration_icicle` chart highlights the **main filtering path** (the sequence of subsets that passed each filter step) with **yellow dots** ●.

When you **click on a subset** in the chart, it zooms in to show a more detailed view, allowing for easier comparison between branches.

How the `query_exploration_icicle(...)` Chart Is Built

1. Retrieve the query history (lineage)

When you pass a result set name (e.g. `'rs_HighValue'`) to the `query_exploration_icicle(...)` function, it first looks up how that result set was created — including all the queries applied in order. This is called the *lineage*, and it includes the original log, each filter step, and the corresponding query names.

2. Load the initial source log

The chart starts from the original dataset (before any filters). This log is retrieved from the registry as the **initial source log**.

3. Add case-level metrics

Depending on the metric you're analyzing (`avg_case_duration_seconds`, `avg_events_per_case`, or `avg_time_between_events`), the function adds one of the following columns:

- Case duration (time from first to last event in the case)
- Number of events per case
- Average time between events in each case

4. Apply each filter in sequence

For every query in the lineage, the log is split into two subsets:

- ✓ One where cases **pass** the filter
- X One where cases **fail** the filter

Each new subset is labeled and tracked with a growing path of decisions — which forms the basis of the final tree.

5. Track the "main path"

The path that includes only passing filters (i.e. the result set you're analyzing) is marked in the chart with yellow dots (●) to help you identify it.

6. Aggregate case metrics

For every subset (leaf node in the tree), the chart computes:

- The number of unique cases
- The average value for the selected metric (e.g., average case duration)

7. Build the visualization

All labeled subsets are passed to Plotly's `icicle` chart function. Each box in the chart:

- Represents a decision step (filter pass/fail)
- Shows how many cases followed that path
- Is color-coded by the chosen metric for easy comparison

Figure 5.3: Part of the content of the tutorial notebook. The notebook aimed to show the participants how the framework works, how to use it, and what it can be used for.

Explore and Apply Filters

In this step, you're going to explore **one** of the analysis questions below. Each question is designed to help you uncover **differences in process behavior** using specific filtering conditions.

1. Do high-value new applications that end up in a successful loan application tend to follow longer or more complex processes than those that don't?

Filter hints:

```
GreaterThanConstant('RequestedAmount', 10000) # High-value application
EqToConstant('ApplicationType', 'New')        # New application
EqToConstant('event', 'A_Pending')           # Successful outcome
```

2. Do in-person submitted applications for car loans perform differently than digital submissions, especially when the requested amount is over €5,000?

Filter hints:

```
EqToConstant('event', 'A_Submitted')         # In-person submitted applications
EqToConstant('LoanGoal', 'Car')             # Loan goals is car
GreaterThanConstant('RequestedAmount', 5000) # Requested amount is over €5,000
```

Getting Started

Make sure you've instantiated your LogView object:

```
log_view = LogViewBuilder.build_log_view(log)
```

You can retrieve the full summary of your session's filtering history at any point:

```
summary = log_view.get_summary()
```

Figure 5.4: Part of the content of the testing notebook.

5.3 User Study: Data Analysis

The analysis combined both quantitative survey responses and qualitative interview data. The questionnaire data was exported from Microsoft Forms and responses were visualized and inspected in Python to identify strong aspects of the framework (where participants consistently rated items highly), weaknesses or limitations (where ratings clustered low), and areas of disagreement (where responses varied strongly). This quantitative inspection aligned with the evaluation goal of identifying broad strengths and the weaknesses of the framework's implementation.

The qualitative part was based on transcriptions of the recorded study sessions, generated using the built-in Microsoft Teams transcription tool [38]. These transcripts were imported into MAXQDA [39] and analyzed using a combination of inductive thematic coding and content analysis. An initial round of open coding was conducted, in which all segments where participants commented on, interacted with, or reflected upon the framework were labeled. Segments such as reading the questionnaire statements aloud were excluded, while segments signaling confusion, discovery of features, failed attempts, or successful task completion were included. In the next step, the extracted codes were grouped into broader response categories: positive comments, negative or improvement suggestions, and use in practice. This distinction aligns with the objective of the thesis; to understand how analysts can best be supported in their work. Positive comments highlight aspects of the approach or implementation that successfully contribute to this goal, indicating where the framework already provides analytical value or usability benefits. Conversely, negative or improvement-oriented remarks point to elements that currently hinder support and therefore represent opportunities for refinement. Through an iterative bottom-up process, these categories were refined into subthemes such as colors, layout, interactivity, metrics, and insight generation. Finally, these subthemes were organized into overarching thematic domains: analytical value, visualization value, and use in practice. The full coding schema is presented in Appendix C.

As a result, the final themes and supporting tables in the following section reveal both strengths and limitations of the current implementation, providing an overview of where the framework effectively supports analysis and where further development could enhance its usefulness.

5.4 User Study: Results

5.4.1 Analytical Value

This section addresses **EQ1: Analytical Value**: *To what extent does the framework support analysts in exploring event logs?*. The purpose of this analysis is to determine whether the framework helps analysts generate insights, understand relationships within the event log, and reflect on their analytical steps. To answer this question, multiple data sources were combined: the *think-aloud protocol* captured participants' reasoning and discoveries during the supervised analysis task, while reflections from the *ICE-T questionnaire* and *open-ended interview questions* provided additional perspectives on the framework's effectiveness in supporting exploration and understanding. These data were analyzed thematically to evaluate how the framework contributed to insight generation, comprehension of filtering sequences, and awareness of the overall analysis process.

This part of the study evaluates the framework with a focus on its contribution to analytical value during the exploration process. The goal was to assess whether the framework helps analysts generate new insights into the event log under investigation and supports reflection on their analytical practices. The results are based on thematic analysis of think-aloud protocols during the supervised task, reflections while completing the ICE-T questionnaire, and responses to open-ended questions.

Table 5.1: Evaluation of Analytical Value (#P = participants, #S = statements)

(a) Positive Aspects			
Aspect	#P	#S	Example Statement
Metrics	6	14	“... the first two metrics, average case duration and events per case, are very good ... useful general metrics to start with ...” (p6) “... the different metrics offered might provide valuable insights you did not expect ... for me this was the case when I looked at the average events per case ...” (p2)
Insights	8	39	“... the visualisation facilitates seeing relationships in the data ... very useful to understand patterns and distributions of variables ...” (p8) “... you could use this to check compliance or compare performances of different selections ... it gives a first insight into how the process behaves over time ...” (p2)
Perspectives	7	19	“... I could see two perspectives ... the data perspective and then also the process perspective ...” (p3) “... the visualisation shows a different perspective ... the pie chart compared to the icicle makes you ask different questions ...” (p7)
Overview	7	27	“... if you want to look for the bigger picture ... it helps me understand each column as one of the filters applied ... so I can see the distribution ...” (p6) “... sometimes it’s very difficult to remember the filters you applied before ... this makes it easier to follow the analysis and understand how results are related to previous steps ...” (p8)

(b) Suggested Improvements			
Aspect	#P	#S	Example Statement
Metric options	9	27	“... I think generally KPI would be interesting ... for example in a banking process I would like to know the requested amount and how often longer cases with large amounts are rejected ...” (p3) “... you can’t really explore frequency metrics ... it would be useful to include absolute frequency, case frequency, or maximum repetitions of cases ...” (p8)
Missing information	8	40	“... it would be useful to include numbers directly in the chart ... the size of the rectangle shows it roughly, but it would be very nice to see the actual case counts ...” (p7) “... maybe hovering over and seeing some percentages or proportions of cases would be useful ... right now it’s just patterns, but for showing results you would need the numbers ...” (p9)
Specific cases	6	6	“... I couldn’t dive down to the single data case ... I can just go to the last cluster, but not the individual case and its attributes ...” (p7) “... you cannot see all the patterns and deviations of each case ...” (p1)
Invalid data	1	2	“... you could get a little label of how many invalid data points there are ... but then you have to define what is an invalid data point ...” (p1)
Query options	2	4	“... the query universe and predicates can be a bit limited ... sometimes you would prefer to manipulate the data directly, like creating a new column, instead of using a union ...” (p6) “... in this experiment I worked mostly with attribute-based predicates, but I would need to look into control-flow predicates as well ...” (p6)
Object centric logs	1	1	“... I’ve worked with object-centric logs ... maybe the amount of objects participating in a case could be interesting as an expansion in that direction ...” (p6)

The results show that participants consistently recognized strong analytical value in the framework. The metrics were highlighted as useful starting points, often revealing unexpected insights. Many participants found that the framework enabled them to identify relationships and patterns in the data, which supported tasks such as compliance checking or performance comparison. They also valued the possibility of approaching the log from different perspectives. Another frequently mentioned strength was the overview of filtering history, which helped participants retain a sense of the bigger picture.

At the same time, several limitations were raised that highlight opportunities for improvement. Participants asked for a broader range of metrics, including KPIs and frequency-based measures. They also mentioned that numerical values, such as case counts or percentages, should be displayed directly within the visualizations. Another recurring theme was the desire to drill down into individual cases to examine their attributes in detail. A few participants pointed to issues such as the handling of invalid data, the limited flexibility of query options, and the lack of support for object-centric logs.

5.4.2 Visualization Value

This section addresses **EQ2: Visualization Value**: *How do users perceive implementation aspects of the framework, such as its usability, clarity, and interactivity?* The goal of this part of the evaluation is to examine how participants experienced the prototype in practice, focusing on how effectively the framework communicates information, supports interaction, and facilitates a smooth analytical workflow.

To answer this question, two complementary data sources were analyzed. First, the *ICE-T questionnaire* [36] was used to quantitatively assess participants' perceptions of the visualization across four dimensions: Insight, Confidence, Essence, and Time efficiency. Second, qualitative data were collected through the *think-aloud protocol* during task execution, as well as through open-ended feedback given during and after questionnaire completion. These qualitative reflections contextualize the numerical ratings by revealing concrete examples of where the framework supported or hindered analysis, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of user experience and perceived implementation quality.

ICE-T Questionnaire Results

To evaluate the quality and perceived value of the visualization, the ICE-T questionnaire was used to quantitatively assess participants' perceptions of the prototype. The questionnaire is grounded in Stasko's value equation for visualization quality, expressed as $V = I + C + E + T$ [36], where the overall value V of a visualization is the sum of four components: *Insight (I)* — its ability to help users generate new understanding or formulate insightful questions; *Confidence (C)* — the extent to which users trust the data, their interpretations, and the visualization itself; *Essence (E)* — how well it conveys the overall meaning or “big picture” of the data; and *Time (T)* — the efficiency with which users can perform analytical tasks. Each item in the questionnaire was rated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from *Strongly Disagree* to *Strongly Agree*.

Figure 5.5 presents a heatmap of the responses per question. The darker shading indicates a higher number of responses in a particular category, while cell values represent exact counts. The results show a clear tendency toward positive ratings, with the majority of responses clustering around Agree and Strongly Agree. Neutral responses were less frequent, and negative ratings were rare, appearing mainly in isolated questions. Some variability between questions is visible: while several items reached a high level of agreement (e.g., Q11, Q12, Q15), others displayed a broader spread of opinions (e.g., Q1, Q13, Q21). Overall, the questionnaire results indicate that participants generally perceived the prototype as supportive of their analysis, though certain aspects require refinement.

Thematic Analysis

While the ICE-T questionnaire provided a quantitative overview of how participants rated different aspects of the prototype, the open-ended feedback allows for a more fine-grained understanding of the reasons behind these ratings. The questionnaire results served to indicate which parts of the framework were considered strong or weak, and to what extent, while the qualitative feedback summarized in Table 5.2 captures the concrete experiences and examples that motivated these ratings. The table groups this feedback into positive aspects and suggested improvements, focusing on user experience and visual representation.

Figure 5.5: Heatmap of responses per ICE-T question. Cell values show counts; darker cells indicate higher counts. Questions are grouped by overarching themes (Insight, Time, Essence, Confidence). Answer options: SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, SWD = Somewhat Disagree, N = Neutral, SWA = Somewhat Agree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree.

Table 5.2: Evaluation Implementation (#P = participants, #S = statements)

(a) Positive Aspects			
Aspect	#P	#S	Example Statement
Easy to use	5	9	“... very easy to understand ... the conditions are binary, so it is very straightforward without creating so many branches ...” (p3) “... the visualisations are very good to understand ... it is a very good tool, very useful, and not complex to use ...” (p6)
Intuitive	2	6	“... you like that it really shows all these filtering steps ... more intuitive perception of things ... makes total sense ...” (p9)
Interactivity	4	8	“... in terms of interactivity, drilling down is a good one to reduce the complexity ... zooming out is another way to remove some complexity ...” (p3)
Main path indicator	4	5	“... I think the yellow thing, the yellow dots is nice so that I can see the path ...” (p9)
Colorscheme	2	2	“... the colour scheme is also clear ... only one single colour scheme ... easy to understand.” (p3)
(b) Suggested Improvements			
Aspect	#P	#S	Example Statement
Usability	4	10	“... you still need to know the syntax ... it’s easy to mess it up ... the complexity of the syntax could be lowered a little bit more ...” (p5)
Clarity	3	12	“... it works, no errors ... but could be nice if we had a message saying something ...” (p3)
Interactivity	7	18	“... change their orders ... change filters ... adding more, removing more ... flexibility ...” (p7)
Colorscheme	4	7	“... one suggestion ... you used green and orange and red for two different types ... be aware of people with colour blindness ...” (p4)
Layout	7	27	“... having multiple metrics visualised together ... putting them side by side is not so difficult ... one good improvement ...” (p9)
Textual	4	5	“... it would be better if it just said this is smaller than ... instead of win X ... that would be easier to understand ...” (p2)
Scalability	3	5	“... maybe if you apply more than 10 filters it could be difficult to see all the results of all the possible outcomes ...” (p6)

Several aspects were consistently described positively. Participants emphasized that the framework was generally easy to understand and not perceived as complex to use. They also highlighted its intuitiveness, noting that the visualization of filtering steps made the analysis process easier to follow and helped them make sense of the applied filters. Interactivity was another strong point, as participants appreciated being able to drill down, zoom out, and focus on specific parts of the analysis. In terms of visual elements, the main path indicator was regarded as a clear aid in tracing selections, while the colorscheme was described as simple and effective.

At the same time, participants also described a number of challenges and suggestions for improvement. Ease of use was also mentioned as a point for improvement, as some participants found the syntax prone to errors and suggested that a more user-friendly interface would lower the barrier to use it. Some participants reported moments of confusion, for example mistaking the overall visualization structure for a tree map at first sight. Interactivity was also raised as an area for further development, with requests for more flexibility such as reordering filters, being able to add or remove them, and to be able to compare alternative paths directly. Concerns were raised about accessibility of the colorscheme, particularly for color-blind users. The layout was seen as a possibility for refinement, for example with better support for viewing multiple metrics side by side. Textual clarity also emerged as an area of improvement, for example in the use of technical notations instead of plain descriptions. Multiple participants also questioned the scalability of the framework when a large number of filters were applied.

5.4.3 Use in Practice

This section addresses **EQ3: Use in Practice: *In which contexts and stages of their analytical workflow do analysts consider the framework most valuable?*** The purpose of this part of the evaluation is to explore how the framework could be applied in realistic analytical settings and to identify situations in which it provides the greatest practical benefit.

To answer this question, qualitative data were collected through *interview questions* conducted after the analysis task. These questions encouraged participants to reflect on their own workflows and to describe concrete scenarios where the framework would enhance their work. The resulting responses were thematically analyzed to identify recurring contexts of use, perceived benefits, and potential integration points within real-world analysis processes. Table 5.3 summarizes the main use cases that emerged from this analysis.

Table 5.3: Use in Practice (#P = participants, #S = statements)

Subtheme	#P	#S	Example Statement
Validation	2	2	“... with the visualisation it’s also quite easy to figure out that they did something wrong ... the two columns in the icicle were identical.” (p4)
Answer questions about analysis	3	8	“I have a specific research question ... I first applied the features that helped me to reduce the number of cases ... here is when I could use the icicle function.” (p5)
Presenting the analysis	2	2	“... great to give a quick ... overview ... I would use that with a limited amount of filters ...” (p7) “... in the publications ... it can be used to tell the story ... readers ... like that.” (p9)
Presenting the data	6	16	“... if I would go to the business and show them those visualisations ... mainly the duration and the ... time between events ... the most impactful.” (p7) “... now it’s important to ... register the gender of a student ... if the student is doing this assignment for the first, second, third time ... which attributes are relevant.” (p6)

The responses reveal that participants envisioned diverse applications of the framework. Some emphasized its role in validation, such as identifying mistakes in the data or results. Others highlighted its usefulness for answering specific analytical questions, particularly in reducing cases and focusing on relevant subsets. In addition, participants saw value in presenting the analysis,

for instance in publications or when giving a quick overview of results, and in presenting the data to non-technical audiences such as business stakeholders.

5.5 Algorithmic Performance

The final part of the evaluation answers the last evaluation question **EQ4: Algorithmic Performance**: How does the framework perform in terms of runtime and memory efficiency?

This was done through a series of benchmarks. These benchmarks were designed to assess the scalability and efficiency of the core algorithms underlying the framework, particularly the filtering mechanism and metric computation.

Benchmarks were conducted on scaled versions ($\frac{1}{3}$, $\frac{2}{3}$, $1\times$, $1.5\times$, $2\times$) of the BPI 2017 dataset [1], as well as on synthetic datasets. The scaled BPI logs were generated by sampling or duplicating complete cases from the original event log. For the reduced versions ($\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{2}{3}$), a random subset of cases was selected while preserving the original temporal order of events. For the enlarged versions ($1.5\times$ and $2\times$), additional copies of existing cases were appended, with case identifiers modified (e.g., adding a “_dup” suffix) and timestamps shifted by one day to maintain chronological consistency. This ensured that all scaled logs retained valid process structures and realistic event spacing.

The synthetic logs were created using a controlled event log generator. Each synthetic dataset consisted of cases whose number of events followed a Poisson distribution (mean = 8), with events assigned sequential timestamps uniformly distributed within each case’s duration. Activity labels were drawn from a fixed set of five activities (A0–A4). To evaluate scalability, five synthetic logs were produced with 5k, 10k, 20k, 30k, and 40k cases, each generated using a different random seed to ensure statistical independence.

The evaluation focused on the `apply_filters` function and on the computation of metrics, as these are the most resource-intensive operations. Figures 5.6 and 5.7 report runtime and memory usage across scaled logs and synthetic datasets.

The results demonstrate that runtime and memory usage increase linearly with the size of the event log. This was confirmed both on scaled versions of the BPI 2017 dataset and on synthetic datasets. Lineage construction with the `apply_filters` function and subsequent metric computations follow this linear trend.

These functions calculate metrics not only for the subsets created by analysts, but also for their complements, and this splitting process is repeated at every filter step. Consequently, the number of subsets grows exponentially with the number of filters applied (up to 2^n for n filters). The exponential growth in the number of subsets represents a structural limitation of the framework. While dataset size is the main determinant of performance in the benchmarks, the depth of the applied filter sequence can also have an impact.

Figure 5.6: Apply_filters on the BPI Challenge 2017 log.

(a) Runtime metric calculation (synthetic log).

(b) Memory usage metric calculation (synthetic log).

Figure 5.7: Metric computation performance on synthetic logs.

Together, these components provide a comprehensive evaluation of the framework: the user study focuses on the framework's perceived analytical and experiential value from an end-user perspective, while the algorithmic benchmark validates its technical feasibility and performance under varying data conditions.

Chapter 6

Discussion

The central research question of this thesis was: *How can analysts in exploratory process mining be supported in systematically tracking and visualizing the effects of sequential querying?* This chapter discusses the findings in relation to that question, interpreting how the framework addresses the challenges identified earlier in the thesis.

Section 6.1 addresses EQ1, discussing how the framework supports analysts in exploring event logs, understanding filtering sequences, and developing new insights. Section 6.2 relates to EQ3, identifying the contexts, tasks, and workflow stages in which analysts found the framework most beneficial. Section 6.3 integrates findings for EQ2 and EQ4, examining both user perceptions of usability and interactivity, and the system’s computational performance. Section 6.4 situates the contributions of the framework within existing research. Finally, Section 6.5 reflects on constraints of the study.

6.1 Proposed Solution

This section discusses the extent to which the framework supports analysts in exploring event logs, relating to EQ1: Analytical Value. The evaluation demonstrated that the proposed framework effectively addresses a key challenge in exploratory process mining: enabling analysts not only to apply filters, but also to maintain an overview of how those filters shape their subsequent insights. Participants consistently emphasized the usefulness of the provided metrics, the interpretability of the visualizations, and the value of viewing analyses from multiple perspectives. These findings indicate that the framework supports cognitive continuity by helping analysts remember, compare, and rationalize the sequence of analytical steps they take.

Another contribution lies in the framework’s ability to let analysts move fluidly between perspectives. The ability to view the same log from different analytical angles proved crucial for generating new insights, prompting reflection on assumptions, and uncovering relationships that might otherwise remain hidden.

However, participants also identified limitations that suggest directions for refinement. They expressed a desire for a broader set of domain-specific metrics (e.g., KPIs, frequency-based measures) and the ability to drill down to individual cases. These observations reveal a tension between overview and detail: while analysts appreciate the bird’s-eye perspective provided by the framework, they also want the means to validate patterns at the case level.

6.2 Insights for Analysts

This section explores the contexts and stages in which analysts find the framework most valuable, relating to EQ3: Use in Practice. Demonstrations on three benchmark event logs (BPI 2017 [1], Traffic Fines [40], and Sepsis [3]) showed that the framework supports a variety of analytical objectives across domains. It enables analysts to explore how specific variables affect outcomes,

investigate overlaps between attributes and activities, and assess how these patterns influence process metrics such as duration, number of events, and time between activities. By visualizing the effects of sequential filtering, the framework helps analysts trace how results evolve across multiple steps, supporting both reflection and hypothesis generation.

In the user study, participants contextualized these capabilities within their own workflows. They reported that the framework made relationships intuitive, that the sequential display helped them recall the order of filters, and that unexpected findings prompted new questions. Many participants envisioned practical applications: using the framework to present simplified process overviews to stakeholders, for compliance checking, or for performance monitoring. In academic contexts, participants suggested using it to gain initial insights into new event logs, identify key attributes, and generate hypotheses — or even in teaching, to illustrate how filtering decisions shape analytical outcomes. Overall, participants emphasized that the framework facilitates clearer reasoning, better communication, and more reflective analysis.

6.3 Implementation

This section combines insights from EQ2 and EQ4, exploring how users experienced the prototype’s usability, clarity, and interactivity, and how the framework performed in terms of runtime and memory efficiency. The ICE-T questionnaire results (Figure 5.5) indicate a generally positive reception across dimensions, particularly regarding the framework’s ability to support recognition of relationships between variables (Q2, Q3), to stimulate data-driven questions (Q4), and to provide a coherent overview of results (Q9, Q14). These quantitative results were supported by open-ended feedback (Table 5.2), which provided deeper insights into why certain aspects were praised and where further refinement is needed.

Participants found the framework intuitive and easy to use, noting that the visualization of filtering steps and interactive features such as drilling down and zooming out effectively reduced complexity. Visual elements like the main path indicator and simple color scheme enhanced clarity and interpretability. These strengths suggest that the design decisions successfully supported the goal of maintaining traceability across sequential filtering steps.

Nonetheless, challenges were also reported. Some participants found the query syntax prone to errors and requested a more user-friendly interface. Others suggested improvements to layout clarity, textual labeling, and interactivity — particularly the ability to reorder filters, compare alternative paths, and display multiple metrics side by side. Concerns were also raised regarding color accessibility and the scalability of the framework for long filter sequences.

Complementing these usability results, EQ4 examined algorithmic performance to assess the framework’s computational feasibility. Benchmarks on both real and synthetic datasets showed that runtime and memory usage scale linearly with log size, confirming the approach’s suitability for realistic data volumes. However, the generation of subsets and their complements at each filtering step results in exponential growth in the number of partitions, highlighting a structural limitation for very long filter sequences. While performance was adequate for typical exploratory use cases, this finding underscores the importance of optimizing future implementations for scalability.

6.4 Relation to Existing Work

The framework builds directly on the LogView framework [15], which introduced the idea of a registry to track filters and characterize subsets. This prototype extends that foundation by focusing on exploration and making the lineage of sequential filters and their complements visible to the analyst. While LogView characterizes subsets primarily for validation, the framework repurposes this characterization to support iterative questioning and discovery.

In relation to process cubes [17, 29], the approach employs a similar logic of comparing subsets through metrics but replaces cross-dimensional slicing with the analyst’s own sequence of filters,

thus centering analysis on user-driven actions rather than static data dimensions. Compared to systems such as ProcessExplorer [20], which automate subset selection, this framework preserves analyst agency and emphasizes reflection on the analytical process. Finally, in alignment with interactive systems such as Ziggy [25] and visualization techniques for process data [30, 31], the framework demonstrates how transparent visual encodings can make exploratory analysis more systematic and interpretable.

6.5 Limitations

The evaluation has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the number and diversity of participants were limited, which constrains the generalizability of the findings and may not fully reflect the perspectives of practitioners in different domains. This limitation was partially mitigated by recruiting participants with varying levels of process mining expertise from both academia and industry, ensuring that different analytical backgrounds were represented. Nevertheless, future studies should involve a larger and more heterogeneous participant pool to increase external validity.

Second, the evaluation was based on a predefined task, which introduces a degree of artificiality and may not capture the full complexity of analysts' real-world practices. This was partly mitigated by allowing participants to choose between two task options and to freely apply filters, providing some flexibility and realism. Still, future studies could better capture natural usage patterns and contextual decision-making.

Third, the framework was tested on only three event logs, which limits conclusions about its generalizability to other data types or domains. This was addressed to some extent by selecting logs that varied in domain, structure, and size, covering healthcare, finance, and public administration, to obtain diverse analytical contexts. Future validation on additional datasets would further test the robustness of the approach.

Finally, the thematic coding of open-ended responses may involve some degree of researcher subjectivity, as the coding was performed by a single analyst. This risk was mitigated through a structured, iterative coding procedure and by maintaining detailed documentation of coding decisions. Nonetheless, future work could improve reliability by involving multiple coders and establishing inter-rater agreement measures.

Chapter 7

Conclusion & Future Work

Section 7.1 revisits the central research question and discusses the conceptual and practical contributions of the work. Section 7.2 then identifies opportunities for extending this research.

7.1 Conclusion

The work addressed the central question of how analysts in exploratory process mining can be supported in systematically tracking and visualizing the effects of sequential querying. Both a conceptual framework and a prototype implementation were developed and evaluated. It demonstrated that visualizing filter sequences and their complements helps analysts preserve an overview of their analysis, and stimulates new insights. Characterization of subsets with metrics such as case duration, number of events per case, and time between events further enabled systematic comparison and reflection. Extending the LogView framework, this thesis shifts the role of subset characterization from validating results to stimulating exploration. Instead of limiting its use to confirming predefined expectations, the approach encourages analysts to formulate new questions and pursue their analyses in a more systematic way.

The evaluation showed that the approach is applicable across different kinds of logs and can support both structured analysis tasks and more open-ended exploration. At the same time, several limitations were identified: the participant group was small and homogeneous, the evaluation task was artificial, and only a restricted set of event logs was tested. Moreover, scalability concerns remain with long filter sequences due to the visualization becoming crowded. In summary, the thesis contributes a novel way of making analysts' choices and their consequences transparent in exploratory process mining. By combining visualization with systematic characterization, it provides a foundation for more interactive, flexible, and scalable tools that help analysts preserve context, generate insights, and communicate results effectively.

7.2 Future Work

This study opens several avenues for future research. First, the analytical value of the framework can be strengthened by integrating richer metrics, combining general-purpose measures (e.g., case duration, events per case) with domain-specific indicators such as KPIs or frequency-based metrics. Such extensions would allow the framework to adapt more closely to the needs of practitioners in different domains. Second, the prototype could benefit from enhanced interactivity. Features such as reordering filters, comparing alternative paths, or drilling down to individual cases would provide analysts with greater flexibility and better support for sensemaking across levels of detail. Finally, the framework requires larger-scale evaluations. Studies with a broader range of practitioners and contexts are needed to validate its usefulness beyond controlled settings. Such evaluations should include realistic applications such as business communication, and compliance and performance monitoring.

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Appendix A

Demographics and Experience Questionnaire

The following questionnaire was administered to collect demographic information and better understand participants' experience and expertise with process mining. The survey was estimated to take approximately five minutes to complete.

A.1 Introduction

Dear Participant,

Below you find a short questionnaire to help us gather demographic information and better understand your experience and expertise with process mining. Your responses will support our research on evaluating a new visualization tool designed to assist in process analysis. Thank you in advance for your time and participation!

A.2 Demographic Information

1. Please indicate your age range:
 - 18–24 years old
 - 25–34 years old
 - 35–44 years old
 - 45–54 years old
 - 55–64 years old
 - 65 and over
2. What is your native language?
3. What is your current job position? (Write e.g., “Ph.D. student,” “Master student,” etc. if still pursuing an education.)
4. Which of the following options best describes your current position?
 - I am a master student.
 - I work in academia as a junior researcher or PhD student.
 - I work in academia as a senior researcher or professor.
 - I work in industry.
 - Other
5. In which country do you live?

A.3 Process Mining Experience and Expertise

6. How would you rate your overall process mining expertise?
 - Novice
 - Basic Expertise
 - Average Expertise
 - Good Expertise
 - Advanced Expertise
7. How many years of process mining experience do you have?
 - 0
 - 1
 - 2-3
 - 4-5
 - More than 5
8. How many process mining projects have you participated in within the past three years? (Please count only projects where you analyzed data for a third party such as a company, university project, etc.)
 - 0
 - 1
 - 2-3
 - 4-5
 - More than 5
9. Can you analyze an event log comfortably without the help of a process mining expert?
 - Yes
 - No
10. How many event logs have you analyzed in the past three years?
 - 0
 - 1
 - 2-5
 - More than 5

A.4 Knowledge of Pm4Py

11. Have you used Pm4Py before to analyze or explore an event log?
 - Yes
 - No
12. If yes, can you describe in one sentence in which context/occasion?

Appendix B

ICE-T Questionnaire

The following questionnaire was administered to participants in order to evaluate the visualization according to the ICE-T methodology. Participants were asked to rate their agreement with each statement on a 7-point Likert scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Somewhat Disagree, Neither Agree nor Disagree, Somewhat Agree, Agree, Strongly Agree).

B.1 Insight

1. The visualization exposes individual data cases and their attributes.
2. The visualization facilitates perceiving relationships in the data like patterns and distributions of the variables.
3. The visualization promotes exploring relationships between individual data cases as well as different groupings of data cases.
4. The visualization helps generate data-driven questions.
5. The visualization helps identify unusual or unexpected, yet valid, data characteristics or values.
6. The visualization provides useful interactive capabilities to help investigate the data in multiple ways.
7. The visualization shows multiple perspectives about the data.
8. The visualization uses an effective representation of the data that shows related and partially related data cases.

B.2 Time

9. The visualization provides a meaningful spatial organization of the data.
10. The visualization shows key characteristics of the data at a glance.
11. The interface supports using different attributes of the data to reorganize the visualization's appearance.
12. The visualization supports smooth transitions between different levels of detail in viewing the data.
13. The visualization avoids complex commands and textual queries by providing direct interaction with the data representation.

B.3 Essence

14. The visualization provides a comprehensive and accessible overview of the data.
15. The visualization presents the data by providing a meaningful visual schema.
16. The visualization facilitates generalizations and extrapolations of patterns and conclusions.
17. The visualization helps understand how variables relate in order to accomplish different analytic tasks.

B.4 Confidence

18. The visualization uses meaningful and accurate visual encodings to represent the data.
19. The visualization avoids using misleading representations.
20. The visualization promotes understanding data domain characteristics beyond the individual data cases and attributes.
21. If there were data issues like unexpected, duplicate, missing, or invalid data, the visualization would highlight those issues.

Appendix C

Thematic Coding Scheme

The qualitative data was analyzed in MAXQDA 24 following a thematic coding process. The hierarchical coding structure is presented below, with the number of coded segments shown in parentheses.

Open Coding (270)

- **Good Features (116)**

- Inspiring (5)
- Storytelling (4)
- Yellow dot (4)
- Intuitive (5)
- Interactivity (7)
- Perspectives (18)
- Metrics (13)
- Insights (38)
- Overview (26)
- Easy to use (8)
- Colors (2)

- **Improvements (148)**

- Object centric logs (1)
- Query options (4)
- Ease of use (9)
- Confusion (11)
- Layout (26)
- Textual (4)
- Invalid data (2)
- Specific cases (6)
- Handling many filters (4)
- Colors (6)
- Adding additional information (40)
- Metric options (27)

- Reordering / adding / removing filters / paths (17)
- **Use in Practice (37)**
 - Spotting mistakes (1)
 - Answer questions (3)
 - Overview (11)
 - Publication (1)
 - Generating questions (7)
 - Exploration (6)
 - Business (8)
 - Education (1)